

The nitroacetanilides are reduced at pH 6.1 in a single step which corresponds to a 4-electron reduction process. Thus, the reduction of the nitroacetanilides at this pH is analogous to the reduction of nitrobenzene. The 4-electron reduction process of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-nitroacetanilides represents their reduction to the corresponding phenylhydroxylamine derivatives. Since the plots of $\log k_{f,h}$ vs $E_{a.o.}$ in the presence of different organic solvents are linear, there is only one rate-determining step^{8,9} involved in the electroreduction of each depolariser. The influence of increasing amounts of organic solvents on the kinetics of the irreversible electrode reactions of the nitroacetanilides is discussed below in terms of the values of the kinetic parameters, αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$.

From Table 1 it is evident that the product αn_a decreases with increasing amounts of all the organic solvents. The values of αn_a lie in the range 0.53-0.97 in the presence of different organic solvents. An attempt to estimate n_a , the number of electrons involved in the rate-determining step, apparently leads to a conclusion^{8,10} that n_a is equal to 2 because for totally irreversible systems as the present ones are, α should be less than¹¹ 0.5. However, only a single electron can be transferred at a time during the course of an electrode reaction^{8,9}, a value of n_a exceeding 1 should merely mean that the successive steps are too nearly simultaneous to be distinguished on the time scale implicit in the polarographic measurements. Thus, whether n_a is 1 or 2, the change in αn_a values can only be due to a change in α . It is thus concluded that it is α which is decreasing, thus implies that the transfer of electron(s) is made increasingly difficult. In other words, the electrode reactions of the nitroacetanilides are rendered increasingly more irreversible with increasing amounts of organic solvents.

A perusal of Table 1 reveals that there is no regularity in the variation of $k_{f,h}^0$ values with increasing amounts of organic solvents. It has also been hinted^{5a} at the limitation of $k_{f,h}^0$ in interpreting the results. However, the influence of increasing amounts of organic solvents on the electrode reactions of the nitroacetanilides can be studied in terms of the value of the potential-dependent rate constant ($k_{f,h}$) at a suitable potential which should be such as to lie between the potentials corresponding to the foot and the plateau of the polarographic wave. At such a potential both the rate of the electron-transfer and the diffusion determine the magnitude of the current. In the present study this potential has been taken as -0.36, -0.40 and -0.5 V (vs S.C.E.) for *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-nitroacetanilides, respectively. A perusal of Table 1 shows that $k_{f,h}$ decreases with increasing amounts of organic solvents. From this it follows that the electrode reactions of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-nitroacetanilides are rendered more

irreversible with increasing amounts of the organic solvents. These conclusions are in harmony with those arrived at on the basis of the variation in αn_a values.

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Extraction and Recovery of some Carboxylic Acids by Flexible Polyurethane Foam from Water

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Manuscript received 27 August 1984, revised 17 July 1985,
accepted 29 October 1985

THE discovery of polyurethane foams to retain a number of compounds including polychlorinated biphenyls, organochlorine pesticides, phthalate esters etc. from water¹, developed a growing interest in using this technique to concentrate other compounds as well. Therefore, an attempt has been made to study the column chromatographic behaviour of some carboxylic acids on flexible polyurethane foam plugs in water.

Polyurethane foam plugs of different diameters (d) were cut from 45 mm thick flexible polyurethane foam sheet (J. J. Products, India). Aqueous or ethanolic solutions of carboxylic acids (Sigma) and aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide (Ranbaxy) were prepared. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

To determine the amounts of the carboxylic acids obtained from water, the foam plugs (19 mm d. × 90 mm) were wetted with distilled water for 15 min and placed in a glass column (17 mm i.d.). 0.001 N of the acid solutions (100 ml) were passed through the column at $28 \pm 2^\circ$ and at boiling

temperature. The acids retained by the plug were eluted with ethanol and titrated with 0.01 *N* aqueous sodium hydroxide solution². Polyurethane foam was found to have good retention capacity for cinnamic (69%), indole-3-acetic (62%), β -naphthaleneacetic (85%) and β -naphthoxyacetic (78%) acids. In boiling water the retention capacity for cinnamic, indole-3-acetic and β -naphthaleneacetic acids decreases (10-20%) due to enhanced solubility of the acids in water. However, in the case of β -naphthoxyacetic acid it increases (10%) due to increase in the precipitation.

To study the effect of dilution, aqueous solutions (100 ml) of β -naphthaleneacetic acid with different concentrations were passed through the column and the acid retained was eluted and determined as before. The retention capacity of the foam plug was found to decrease sharply with the dilution of the acid, *i.e.* when concentration decreases to one-tenth, the retention decreases to one-third.

The effect of tightness and length of the foam plug in the column was studied by passing 0.0004 *N* of β -naphthaleneacetic acid (250 ml) through the column containing the foam plugs of different diameters and lengths. The acid retained was determined as before. It was observed that the retention capacity of the foam plug depends on its tightness and length in the column. When a plug of 21 mm (d.) and 45 mm length is fixed in a column of 11 mm (i.d.) the retention of β -naphthaleneacetic acid is 52% and it is 31% on using the same plug in a 17 mm (i.d.) column. The retention capacity also increases with the length of the foam plug. The retention is 99% on using four plugs and it is only 52% on using one plug of 21 mm (d.) and 45 mm length in 11 mm (i.d.) column. The rate of flow also depends on tightness and length of the foam plug. It is appreciable (23 ± 5 ml min⁻¹) with the tightest and the longest plug under study.

A known volume of the synthetic sample of water containing an acid and a foreign substance was passed through the column to study the retention of the acids from saline waters. The acids retained were eluted and determined as before. It was observed that the foam plug has fair retention (37-66%) of β -naphthaleneacetic acid from water containing 74.4 mg dm⁻³ of the acid with (units in ml dm⁻³) acetophenone (0.41), aluminium chloride (0.5), ammonium molybdate (0.5), arsenic oxide (0.05), calcium nitrate (0.7), copper sulphate (1.0), dextrin (20.0), ferrous sulphate (1.5), lead nitrate (0.1), manganese chloride (100.0), mercuric nitrate (0.001), potassium iodide (1.0), potassium sulphate (500.0), silver nitrate (0.05), sodium chloride (350.0), sodium fluoride (0.7), sodium nitrate (10.0), sodium nitrite (10.0), sodium phosphate (0.35), sodium thiosulphate (500.0), stannous chloride (0.7), strontium chloride (2.0), thiourea (2.0) and zinc chloride (5.0). The results suggest the possible use of polyurethane foam plugs for the retention of β -naphthaleneacetic acid from different types of water.

β -Naphthaleneacetic acid can be separated from acetic, benzoic, cinnamic and trichloroacetic acids in water. A definite volume of each acid (1 ml, 0.1 *N*) was taken in a 10 ml standard flask and the total volume was made up with distilled water. This mixture of acids was passed through a column of 11 mm (i.d.) containing two plugs of 21 mm (d.) at the rate of 32 ± 5 ml min⁻¹. The acids were eluted with distilled water (100 ml) and each 10 ml fraction of the effluent was titrated with 0.01 *N* sodium hydroxide solution. β -Naphthaleneacetic acid could not be eluted with water. It was eluted with ethanol (50 ml) and titrated as above. The elution curve was made by plotting the concentration of the acids against the volume of effluents. The sharp elution curve indicates that polyurethane foam plug chromatography is a very simple and fast method of separation.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. M. Qureshi, Chairman, Chemistry Section, Z. H. College of Engineering and Technology, Aligarh Muslim University, for providing facilities and to the C. S. I. R., New Delhi for awarding financial assistance to one of them (S.K.S.).

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Synthesis of New Isomeric Chalcones

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Manuscript received 1 July 1985, accepted 29 October 1985

It has been reported that cinnamoylchalcones can be prepared in good yield from 4,6-diacetylresorcinol^{1,2}. This has prompted us to synthesise two new isomeric substituted derivatives of cinnamoylchalcones. Two isomeric chalcones have been synthesised in good yield from 4,6-diacetylresorcinol (1) and characterised by their uv, ir, nmr and mass spectral data. The two isomers could be differentiated only by their mass fragmentation patterns.

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